

Systematic Review Protocol

Title	Topics, methods and populations in recent randomized controlled trials of interventions around birth and during the neonatal hospitalization for very preterm infants: A systematic review
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¹ Note: this protocol template has been structured around the PRISMA-P checklist based on a format suggested by <https://guides.lib.unc.edu/systematic-reviews/protocol>. See: Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, Ghersi D, Liberati A, Petticrew M, Shekelle P, Stewart L, PRISMA-P Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*. 2015 Jan 2;349(jan02 1):g7647

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and rationale

Very preterm (VPT) birth before 32 weeks' gestation affects 1-2% of babies and is associated with over two-thirds of neonatal deaths in Europe. Compared with children born at term, survivors of VPT birth face high risks of short and long-term health and developmental difficulties. These include cerebral palsy, deficits in vision and hearing, respiratory morbidity, cognitive and motor impairments and emotional and behavioral disorders.¹⁻⁶ A key concern is that these longer-term developmental and health outcomes do not appear to be improving over time despite medical advances that have increased survival.^{7,8}

High-quality randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have played a key role in the advances in obstetrics and neonatal medicine that have vastly improved survival and reduced serious neonatal complications after VPT birth.^{9,10} However, RCTs face limits in addressing many of the urgent questions about the comparative effectiveness of interventions needed to improve outcomes after VPT birth. Organizational and logistic issues affect patient recruitment, restricting samples sizes and generating samples that may not be representative of the target population. Trials tend to be conducted in selected centers that have specialized patient populations and participation is further constrained by the logistic complexities of including these high-risk infants in trials during unexpected, emergency situations when parents are distressed and focused on absorbing new information about their infant's health. A recent study found that VPT trials included only 44% of eligible infants, due to parental refusals, the study not being proposed or other study factors.¹¹

These constraints also constitute a challenge for selecting appropriate patient-valued outcomes that reflect long-term health and development. Long-term developmental outcomes vary widely among children born VPT and, at discharge from the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), each individual VPT baby's prognosis is uncertain.¹² Some children experience no or only mild sequelae, about 10% have severe impairments with lifelong dependency and need for care, and around one third have cognitive, social or emotional difficulties requiring additional support in school.^{1,13-15} Neonatal morbidities (brain lesions, respiratory morbidity, infections) are correlated with adverse longer-term outcomes,^{1,14,16} but improving neonatal outcomes may not map into better long-term child or adult health¹⁰. The efficacy of interventions observed at NICU discharge may persist or accumulate over time to yield long-term benefit or, conversely, diminish over time as the effects of early intervention are washed out. Of most concern are treatments that have beneficial short-term effects, but adverse long-term consequences. There are multiple examples of treatments in neonatal care, proven to be effective, that were later found to increase risks of poor long-term outcomes, for instance, use of the corticosteroid dexamethasone for reducing chronic lung disease.¹⁷ However, despite the recognized importance of including follow-up in trials on VPT infants to measure long-term benefits and to rule out adverse long-term effects, many RCTs only include outcomes before discharge home from the neonatal hospitalization.¹⁸

A consequence of these research constraints is that many common interventions are not backed by high-quality evidence, leading to high variation across hospitals and countries in the care provided to VPT infants.¹⁹⁻²¹ This wide practice variation presents a further constraint for research on comparative effectiveness of intervention because usual care, a common comparator used in trials, can differ widely

across settings.²² Furthermore, large differences in outcomes across units and countries^{23–26} also raise questions about whether the effectiveness of interventions observed in RCTs will be the same in all contexts and, more generally, about the external validity of results.²⁷ These differences also create methodological challenges for trial design, such as for establishing baseline prevalence of mortality and morbidity outcomes and expected effect sizes.

The European IMPROVE PRETERM project (<https://improve-preterm.eu>) aims to improve comparative effectiveness research for therapeutic and preventive healthcare interventions targeting infants born VPT by creating interfaces between randomized trials and cohort and register studies. This study is part of IMPROVE PRETERM's first objective to describe the methodological challenges in research on infants born VPT, to identify capacity gaps, particularly those that might be filled by creating bridges between observational and experimental studies.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of this systematic review is to describe current challenges in RCTs in the VPT population in relation to the themes explored in the IMPROVE PRETERM project by systematically reviewing recent RCTs on interventions around birth or during the neonatal period for infants born <32 weeks of gestation.

Specific aims are to:

1. Provide a structured descriptive overview of these RCTs, including intervention type (e.g. medicinal product, surgery, care policy), setting and design of the trial, the indications (poor growth, respiratory complications, pain etc.), the primary and secondary outcomes, including whether these include assessments after discharge from the neonatal unit, study quality and conclusions;
2. Assess the degree of detail reported in trial publications to describe the populations of included infants and describe variability across trials in baseline characteristics, obstetrical and neonatal management and outcomes (mortality and morbidity) in the control group;
3. Evaluate the process and adequacy of sample size calculations, including hypotheses regarding the prevalence of the primary outcome, whether empirical data were used to support these hypotheses, the source of the empirical data (literature, existing observational or experimental studies or register data, or pilot data collected for the study), whether the hypotheses were accurate and the impact of any errors in sample size calculation on study precision.

2. Methods

2.1 Eligibility criteria

Population

Included

Participants are very preterm infants (VPT: birth before 32 weeks of gestation) included in recent RCTs of healthcare interventions around birth and during the neonatal hospitalization published from 1st January 2024 up to the final search date. Specifically,

- infants <32 weeks of gestation, even if the study targets a more specific gestational age group within the very preterm population (i.e. extremely preterm only);
- infants born <1500 grams or using other gestational age cutoffs if >90% of inclusions in the RCTs are <32 weeks of gestation and the intervention is intended for care of very preterm infants.

Rationale: Instead of using a gestational age limit only to define our population, we will include some flexibility in the criteria, as described above. This flexibility is necessary to ensure inclusion of all relevant studies for evidence synthesis as many studies on infants born VPT use slightly different inclusion criteria which can lead to omission of important studies when overly restrictive criteria are applied.^{2,28}

Studies

Included

- Phase III RCTs;
- Publications of long-term outcomes after follow-up with regard to the investigated intervention, regardless of whether these are the primary or secondary outcomes or designed as a cohort study following up participants of the phase III RCT;
- Published in PubMed between 1/1/2024 and final update;
- Published in indexed Q1 and Q2 journals based on SCImago Journal Rank (SJR), Scopus data / Clarivate JCR, Web of Science data in 2024. If a journal is ranked in multiple disciplines, we will consider the highest quartile.

Excluded

- Interim publications of RCT results;
- RCT pilot studies or trials of feasibility;
- Publications of study protocols, preprints or statistical analysis plans;
- Phase I, II and IV studies;
- Secondary studies of RCTs, i.e. use of RCTs for secondary analyses or studies focusing only on the RCT's secondary outcomes when these are not follow-up outcomes;
- Studies focusing on children with specific congenital or endocrine anomalies only;
- Studies in Q3 and Q4 journals based on criteria described above.

Additional exclusions for the sample size sub study:

- Studies that are not parallel, 2 arm superiority RCT (i.e. exclusion of non-inferiority or equivalence trials, cluster and crossover and factorial designs);
- Studies without mortality outcomes, disease prevalence or developmental outcomes (e.g. patient satisfaction, process outcomes, health-service outcomes);
- Studies with multiple primary outcomes.

Rationale: The criterion in relation to journal rank (Q1 and Q2 journals only) aims to include highest quality studies published in journals which constitute the body of work used by clinicians and

researchers to define evidence-based care. Other reviews seeking to focus on high-quality studies have limited their search to the highest-ranking or most renowned journals in their fields.^{29–31} However, we sought to be more inclusive across disciplines, while restricting our sample to studies most likely to contribute to clinical practice guidelines and health policy. To validate this choice, we undertook a review of recent evidence briefs on the EBNEO website (<https://ebneo.org/category/reviews/>). This website aims to provide commentary on RCTs providing new evidence for practice. All recent briefs reviewed were published in journals that would be included in our study. These journals are all indexed on PubMed.

2.2 Information sources

PubMed, published from 1/1/2024 to final update.

2.3 Search Strategy

We will use broad keywords in the search to identify preterm populations, including preterm, low birthweight, neonat*, premature infant and premature newborn.²⁸

To identify RCTs, we will use the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity-maximizing version PubMed format (2008 revision),³² as follows:

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((randomized controlled trial[pt] OR controlled clinical trial[pt] OR randomized[tiab] OR placebo[tiab] OR clinical trials as topic[mesh:noexp] OR randomly[tiab] OR trial[ti]) NOT (animals[mh] NOT humans[mh])) AND((preterm) OR (neonat*) OR (low birthweight) OR (premature infant) OR (premature newborn)) AND (2024/1/1:3000/12/12[pdat])
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[pt] denotes a Publication Type term;

[tiab] denotes a word in the title or abstract;

[sh] denotes a subheading;

[mh] denotes a Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) term ('exploded');

[mesh: noexp] denotes a Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) term (not 'exploded');

[ti] denotes a word in the title.

Only the PubMed database will be searched, since the inclusion criteria require publication in a PubMed indexed medical journal.

To ensure completeness, we will also cross-check our results with PubMed's built-in RCT filter.

2.4 Study records

2.4.2. Data management

Records will be sought from PubMed database and will be imported into Endnote and Zotero for initial screening.

2.4.3. Selection process

After excluding irrelevant studies, titles and abstracts will be independently screened by two reviewers (MK, SB). Disagreements will be resolved by the third reviewer (JZ) through discussion. Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>) will be used for this process.

2.4.4. Data collection process

Data will be extracted independently by at least one person and one person-machine combination with differences resolved by a third reviewer through discussion. When data is not available in published reports/protocols, corresponding authors will be contacted to provide any required data. The abstraction process will be done using a structured LimeSurvey questionnaire with closed and open questions which can be exported to excel. For the machine process, we will use a standardized, pretested prompt with the same structured questionnaire format, allowing results to be exported in the same Excel format for final validation by the reviewer.

2.5 Data Items

Reviewer pairs will independently extract the data items listed below. One of the reviewers will use a machine to complete a structured abstraction form and check the responses against the original article while a second reviewer will complete abstraction with the same structured form using LimeSurvey. Abstracted data will be compared and discrepancies will be resolved by discussion or by a third reviewer.

Design and Methodology:

- Study design (e.g. cluster/crossover, superiority, non-inferiority, equivalence);
- Description of randomization (e.g. randomization unit, stratification criteria);
- Type of intervention (medicinal product, surgery, care practice, other) and other (prophylactic versus treatment)
- Indication/Health problem (nutrition, respiratory complications, neurological complications);
- Blinding (blinded personnel in the trial);
- Engagement in the study design of people with lived experience of preterm birth;
- Trial registration and publication of protocol and statistical analysis plan (SAP).

Population description:

- Study centers (location of study – single country vs multinational, number of centers – single vs multi, eligibility/exclusion criteria of study center(s));
- Study population (inclusion, exclusion criteria);
- The clinical and sociodemographic variables presented in the manuscript allowing description of the children included in the study (e.g. maternal and pregnancy characteristics, socio-economic information, maternal medical history/obstetric complications, perinatal management, birth complications, neonatal characteristics, neonatal management, other health complications);
- Study recruitment (% approached, % consented, % secondary refusals);
- The proportion of children lost to follow-up and characteristics of those lost to follow-up if outcomes after discharge from neonatal unit.

Outcome:

- Outcome measures (primary and secondary, timing of outcome (postmenstrual age (PMA) at evaluation and/or age after discharge home from the neonatal unit);
- Whether the authors used a core outcome set to select and define outcomes;
- Adverse effects;
- Effect measures for short and long-term outcomes (means and standard deviations/proportions of primary and secondary outcomes). Missing values (e.g. standard

deviation) will be calculated from the available data (p-values, t-values, confidence intervals or standard errors;

- Conclusion of trial (significant results, level of significance, etc).

Sample size sub study:

- Data for sample size calculations: (1) the expected event rate (baseline risk) for the primary outcome (2) the target difference in effect anticipated with the intervention (absolute or relative risk reduction) (3) desired type I and type II error. Information on how the expected event rate was obtained (sources of data);
- Data to evaluate accuracy of assumptions used for the sample sizes: observed event rate in the control population and actual effect sizes;
- If secondary outcomes, power to detect differences, including consideration of loss to follow-up after discharge.

We will use the registered protocols to obtain information that is not available in the published study. Corresponding authors will be contacted to obtain further missing information.

Rationale: to develop the list of data items to be abstracted, we consulted the literature in obstetrics, neonatology and other disciplines in order to identify relevant variables in previous studies that evaluated RCTs on specific topics or evaluated the adequacy of sample size calculations.^{31,33,34} We aimed to create closed responses as much as possible to facilitate cross-checking of data between reviewers, while leading open ended questions for clarification and detail. For the selection of characteristics of the populations, we based the list of variables on harmonized perinatal data dictionaries within the RECAP Preterm platform which were developed within a common schema,³⁵ and work within this platform on a core dataset.³⁶

2.6. Outcomes and prioritization

The primary outcomes in this study are methodological characteristics of the included studies and the characteristics of the patients included in the study. We will record/extract data on trial setting, population, population, interventions, outcome and the methods used to calculate the sample size criteria.

In the sample size sub-study, the primary outcome will be the difference between the value of the expected primary outcome used for sample size calculations and the value of the observed primary outcome in the control population.

2.7 Risk of bias in individual studies

Studies will be assessed independently by at least two people using Cochrane RoB2 tool at the study level rather than at the outcome measure level.

2.8 Data synthesis

The first aim of this review is to describe the characteristics of included RCTs. Data synthesis will be descriptive and structured according to key study characteristics. We will summarize study characteristics using counts, proportions, and measures of central tendency (e.g., means, medians, and ranges, where appropriate). Study characteristics and outcomes of RCTs will be stratified and compared across relevant domains, including journal type, geographic location, study design, population characteristics, indications, type of intervention, and study quality (assessed using risk of bias tools). A narrative synthesis will be used to summarize findings and identify trends, gaps, and

methodological challenges across trials. No meta-analysis is planned due to the heterogeneity of indications, interventions and outcomes.

For the second aim of this systematic review, we will assess available data to describe the populations of infants included in the trials (using as a reference descriptors and outcomes included in recommended core outcome sets for VPT research). We will then compare populations across studies using a sub-set of these core descriptor variables which are available in a majority of studies. We will compare variables' means, variances and distributions.

In addition, we will conduct a sub-study of the procedures and their adequacy for determining the sample sizes for the RCTs. We will describe sources of data used to establish the prevalence of the primary outcome for sample size calculations and the methods used to compute the required sample size. If data are provided (in published article or protocol), we will recalculate the sample size based on the assumptions made by authors and check its consistency with the recruited sample size, given previous findings showing frequent discrepancies.³⁷ When observed event rates/values differ from expected event rates/values, we will quantify the impact by calculating the sample size required for the study if the authors had had accurate information on their primary outcome in their study population, keeping all other hypotheses used by the authors for the sample size calculations constant.

In this sub-study, we will also compute the percent difference between the observed and the expected event rate/values and use forest plots to visualize these differences. Heterogeneity in this difference across studies will be assessed by visual inspection of the forest plot and computation of the tau statistic. We will compute prediction intervals for any pooled estimate of the difference. Since we anticipate variation between studies, meta-analysis will be carried out using the random effects model. The Mantel-Haenszel method will be used for dichotomous outcomes and the Inverse Variance method will be used for continuous outcomes.

2.9 Meta-bias(es)

We will visualize results on outcomes using funnel plots if we have a sufficient number of studies on similar interventions to assess publication bias.

2.10 Confidence in cumulative evidence

Confidence in cumulative evidence will not be assessed.

3. Patient and public involvement

We will include a data item on whether parents' or caregivers' lived experiences of VPT birth were collected and/or reported as part of the trial design.

Results from this study will contribute to a workshop with parents on core outcomes for research on VPT populations that will be held in March 2026.

4. Reviewer contributions

- Jennifer Zeitlin: study design, data screening and data analysis, data synthesis
- Mihyeon Kim: study design, data screening and data analysis, data synthesis
- Soodabeh Behboodi: study design, data screening and data analysis, data synthesis
- Tamara Maziashvili: data analysis, data synthesis
- Andrei Morgan: data analysis, data synthesis
- Moreno Ursino: data analysis, data synthesis
- Jennifer Hutcheon: data analysis, data synthesis

5. Timeline

- Start date: 1 May 2025. End date: 31 May 2026.

6. References

- (1) Pierrat, V.; Marchand-Martin, L.; Marret, S.; Arnaud, C.; Benhammou, V.; Cambonie, G.; Debillon, T.; Dufourg, M.-N.; Gire, C.; Goffinet, F.; Kaminski, M.; Lapillonne, A.; Morgan, A. S.; Rozé, J.-C.; Twilhaar, S.; Charles, M.-A.; Ancel, P.-Y. Neurodevelopmental Outcomes at Age 5 among Children Born Preterm: EPIPAGE-2 Cohort Study. *BMJ* **2021**, *373*, n741. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n741>.
- (2) Sentenac, M.; Boutron, I.; Draper, E. S.; Kajantie, E.; Maier, R. F.; Wolke, D.; Zeitlin, J. Defining Very Preterm Populations for Systematic Reviews With Meta-Analyses. *JAMA Pediatr.* **2020**, *174* (10), 997–999. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.0956>.
- (3) Doyle, L. W.; Andersson, S.; Bush, A.; Cheong, J. L. Y.; Clemm, H.; Evensen, K. A. I.; Gough, A.; Halvorsen, T.; Hovi, P.; Kajantie, E.; Lee, K. J.; McGarvey, L.; Narang, I.; Näsänen-Gilmore, P.; Steinshamn, S.; Vollsaeter, M.; Vrijlandt, E. J. L. E. Expiratory Airflow in Late Adolescence and Early Adulthood in Individuals Born Very Preterm or with Very Low Birthweight Compared with Controls Born at Term or with Normal Birthweight: A Meta-Analysis of Individual Participant Data. *Lancet Respir. Med.* **2019**, *7* (8), 677–686. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(18\)30530-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(18)30530-7).
- (4) Spittle, A. J.; McGinley, J. L.; Thompson, D.; Clark, R.; FitzGerald, T. L.; Mentiplay, B. F.; Lee, K. J.; Olsen, J. E.; Burnett, A.; Treyvaud, K.; Josev, E.; Alexander, B.; Kelly, C. E.; Doyle, L. W.; Anderson, P. J.; Cheong, J. L. Motor Trajectories from Birth to 5 Years of Children Born at Less than 30 Weeks' Gestation: Early Predictors and Functional Implications. Protocol for a Prospective Cohort Study. *J. Physiother.* **2016**, *62* (4), 222–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphys.2016.07.002>.
- (5) Heikkilä, K.; Metsälä, J.; Pulakka, A.; Nilsen, S. M.; Kivimäki, M.; Risnes, K.; Kajantie, E. Preterm Birth and the Risk of Multimorbidity in Adolescence: A Multiregister-Based Cohort Study. *Lancet Public Health* **2023**, *8* (9), e680–e690. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(23\)00145-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(23)00145-7).
- (6) Nilsen, S. M.; Valand, J.; Rogne, T.; Asheim, A.; Yin, W.; Metsälä, J.; Opdahl, S.; Døllner, H.; Damås, J. K.; Kajantie, E.; Solligård, E.; Sandin, S.; Risnes, K. Gestational Age at Birth and Hospitalisations for Infections among Individuals Aged 0–50 Years in Norway: A Longitudinal, Register-Based, Cohort Study. *eClinicalMedicine* **2023**, *62*, 102108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.102108>.
- (7) Cheong, J. L. Y.; Anderson, P. J.; Burnett, A. C.; Roberts, G.; Davis, N.; Hickey, L.; Carse, E.; Doyle, L. W.; Group, V. I. C. S. Changing Neurodevelopment at 8 Years in Children Born Extremely Preterm since the 1990s. *Pediatrics* **2017**, *139* (6), e20164086. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-4086>.
- (8) Behboodi, S.; Chaimani, A.; Benhammou, V.; Twilhaar, E. S.; Johnson, S.; Zeitlin, J.; Sentenac, M. Trends Over Time in Cognitive Outcomes of Children Born Very Preterm: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *JAMA Pediatr.* **2025**. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2025.2221>.
- (9) Soll, R. F.; Ovelman, C.; McGuire, W. The Future of Cochrane Neonatal. *Early Hum. Dev.* **2020**, *150*, 105191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2020.105191>.
- (10) Stoll, B. J.; Hansen, N. I.; Bell, E. F.; Walsh, M. C.; Carlo, W. A.; Shankaran, S.; Laptook, A. R.; Sánchez, P. J.; Van Meurs, K. P.; Wyckoff, M.; Das, A.; Hale, E. C.; Ball, M. B.; Newman, N. S.; Schibler, K.; Poindexter, B. B.; Kennedy, K. A.; Cotten, C. M.; Watterberg, K. L.; D'Angio, C. T.; DeMauro, S. B.; Truog, W. E.; Devaskar, U.; Higgins, R. D.; for the Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Neonatal Research Network. Trends in Care Practices, Morbidity,

- and Mortality of Extremely Preterm Neonates, 1993–2012. *JAMA* **2015**, *314* (10), 1039–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.10244>.
- (11) Shaikh, H.; Lyle, A. N. J.; Oslin, E.; Gray, M. M.; Weiss, E. M. Eligible Infants Included in Neonatal Clinical Trials and Reasons for Noninclusion: A Systematic Review. *JAMA Netw. Open* **2024**, *7* (10), e2441372. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.41372>.
- (12) Webbe, J. W. H.; Duffy, J. M. N.; Afonso, E.; Al-Muzaffar, I.; Brunton, G.; Greenough, A.; Hall, N. J.; Knight, M.; Latour, J. M.; Lee-Davey, C.; Marlow, N.; Noakes, L.; Nycyk, J.; Richard-Löndt, A.; Wills-Eve, B.; Modi, N.; Gale, C. Core Outcomes in Neonatology: Development of a Core Outcome Set for Neonatal Research. *Arch. Dis. Child. Fetal Neonatal Ed.* **2020**, *105* (4), 425–431. <https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2019-317501>.
- (13) Alterman, N.; Johnson, S.; Carson, C.; Petrou, S.; Kurinzczuk, J. J.; Macfarlane, A.; Boyle, E.; Quigley, M. A. Gestational Age at Birth and Academic Attainment in Primary and Secondary School in England: Evidence from a National Cohort Study. *PLOS ONE* **2022**, *17* (8), e0271952. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271952>.
- (14) Serenius, F.; Ewald, U.; Farooqi, A.; Fellman, V.; Hafström, M.; Hellgren, K.; Maršál, K.; Ohlin, A.; Olhager, E.; Stjernqvist, K.; Strömberg, B.; Ådén, U.; Källén, K.; for the Extremely Preterm Infants in Sweden Study Group. Neurodevelopmental Outcomes Among Extremely Preterm Infants 6.5 Years After Active Perinatal Care in Sweden. *JAMA Pediatr.* **2016**, *170* (10), 954–963. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2016.1210>.
- (15) Moore, T.; Hennessy, E. M.; Myles, J.; Johnson, S. J.; Draper, E. S.; Costeloe, K. L.; Marlow, N. Neurological and Developmental Outcome in Extremely Preterm Children Born in England in 1995 and 2006: The EPICure Studies. *BMJ* **2012**, *345* (dec04 3), e7961–e7961. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e7961>.
- (16) Doyle, L. W.; Spittle, A.; Anderson, P. J.; Cheong, J. L. Y. School-Aged Neurodevelopmental Outcomes for Children Born Extremely Preterm. *Arch. Dis. Child.* **2021**, *106* (9), 834–838. <https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2021-321668>.
- (17) Doyle, L. W.; Cheong, J. L.; Ehrenkranz, R. A.; Halliday, H. L. Early (< 8 Days) Systemic Postnatal Corticosteroids for Prevention of Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia in Preterm Infants - Doyle, LW - 2017 | Cochrane Library.
- (18) Marlow, N.; Doyle, L. W.; Anderson, P.; Johnson, S.; Bhatt-Mehta, V.; Natalucci, G.; Darlow, B. A.; Davis, J. M.; Turner, M. A. Assessment of Long-Term Neurodevelopmental Outcome Following Trials of Medicinal Products in Newborn Infants. *Pediatr. Res.* **2019**, *86* (5), 567–572. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-019-0526-1>.
- (19) Wolf, H. T.; Weber, T.; Schmidt, S.; Norman, M.; Varendi, H.; Piedvache, A.; Zeitlin, J.; Huusom, L. D.; Group, E. R. Mode of Delivery and Adverse Short- and Long-Term Outcomes in Vertex-Presenting Very Preterm Born Infants: A European Population-Based Prospective Cohort Study. *J. Perinat. Med.* **2021**, *49* (7), 923–931. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jpm-2020-0468>.
- (20) Parikh, S.; Reichman, B.; Kusuda, S.; Adams, M.; Lehtonen, L.; Vento, M.; Norman, M.; San Feliciano, L.; Isayama, T.; Hakansson, S.; Helenius, K.; Bassler, D.; Yang, J.; Shah, P. S. Trends, Characteristic, and Outcomes of Preterm Infants Who Received Postnatal Corticosteroid: A Cohort

Study from 7 High-Income Countries. *Neonatology* **2023**, *120* (4), 517–526.

<https://doi.org/10.1159/000530128>.

(21) Duffett, M.; Choong, K.; Hartling, L.; Menon, K.; Thabane, L.; Cook, D. J. Randomized Controlled Trials in Pediatric Critical Care: A Scoping Review. *Crit. Care* **2013**, *17* (5), R256.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/cc13083>.

(22) Kirpalani, H.; Truog, W. E.; D'Angio, C. T.; Cotten, M. Recent Controversies on Comparative Effectiveness Research Investigations: Challenges, Opportunities, and Pitfalls. *Semin. Perinatol.* **2016**, *40* (6), 341–347. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.semperi.2016.05.004>.

(23) Hollens, G.; Schindler, T.; Battin, M.; Klinger, G.; Adams, M.; Vento, M.; Santacroce, A.; Håkansson, S.; Isayama, T.; Norman, M.; Kusuda, S.; Lehtonen, L.; Helenius, K.; Modi, N.; Shah, P. S.; Lui, K. International Variation and Trends of Intraventricular Hemorrhage in Very Preterm Infants.

(24) Klinger, G.; Reichman, B.; Norman, M.; Kusuda, S.; Battin, M.; Helenius, K.; Isayama, T.; Lui, K.; Adams, M.; Vento, M.; Hakansson, S.; Beltempo, M.; Poggi, C.; San Feliciano, L.; Lehtonen, L.; Bassler, D.; Yang, J.; Shah, P. S.; on behalf of the International Network for Evaluating Outcomes of Neonates (iNeo). Late-Onset Sepsis among Extremely Preterm Infants of 24–28 Weeks Gestation: An International Comparison in 10 High-Income Countries. *Neonatology* **2024**, *121* (6), 761–771.

<https://doi.org/10.1159/000539245>.

(25) Draper, E. S.; Manktelow, B. N.; Cuttini, M.; Maier, R. F.; Fenton, A. C.; Van Reempts, P.; Bonamy, A.-K.; Mazela, J.; Børch, K.; Koopman-Esseboom, C.; Varendi, H.; Barros, H.; Zeitlin, J. J.; EPICE Cohort. Variability in Very Preterm Stillbirth and In-Hospital Mortality Across Europe. *Pediatrics* **2017**, *139* (4), e20161990. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1990>.

(26) Edstedt Bonamy, A. K.; Zeitlin, J.; Piedvache, A.; Maier, R. F.; van Heijst, A.; Varendi, H.; Manktelow, B. N.; Fenton, A.; Mazela, J.; Cuttini, M.; Norman, M.; Petrou, S.; Reempts, P. V.; Barros, H.; Draper, E. S. Wide Variation in Severe Neonatal Morbidity among Very Preterm Infants in European Regions. *Arch. Dis. Child. Fetal Neonatal Ed.* **2019**, *104* (1), F36–F45.

<https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2017-313697>.

(27) Doyle, J. L. Y., L. W. ;. Mainzer, R. ;. Cheong. Systemic Postnatal Corticosteroids, Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia, and Survival Free of Cerebral Palsy. *JAMA Pediatr* **2025**, *179* (1), 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2024.4575>.

(28) Sentenac, M.; Chaimani, A.; Twilhaar, S.; Benhammou, V.; Johnson, S.; Morgan, A.; Zeitlin, J. The Challenges of Heterogeneity in Gestational Age and Birthweight Inclusion Criteria for Research Synthesis on Very Preterm Birth and Childhood Cognition: An Umbrella Review and Meta-Regression Analysis. *Paediatr. Perinat. Epidemiol.* **2022**, *36* (5), 717–725. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppe.12846>.

(29) Ditter, K. C.; Crowe, E. H.; Mendez-Figueroa, H.; Gupta, M.; Bartal, M. F.; Chauhan, S. P.; Wagner, S. Obstetrical Randomized Controlled Trials: Individuals Screened, Approached, and Enrolled. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol. MFM* **2022**, *4* (3), 100564.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajogmf.2022.100564>.

(30) Doulaveris, G.; Vani, K.; Saccone, G. *Number and quality of randomized controlled trials in obstetrics published in the top general medical and obstetrics and gynecology journals.*

[https://www.ajogmf.org/article/S2589-9333\(21\)00204-4/ppt](https://www.ajogmf.org/article/S2589-9333(21)00204-4/ppt) (accessed 2025-09-19).

- (31) Charles, P.; Giraudeau, B.; Dechartres, A.; Baron, G.; Ravaud, P. Reporting of Sample Size Calculation in Randomised Controlled Trials: Review. *BMJ* **2009**, *338* (may12 1), b1732–b1732. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.b1732>.
- (32) Cochrane. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions (2008 Revision)*; https://handbook-5-1cochraneorg/chapter_6/6_4_11_1_the_cochrane_highly_sensitive_search_strategies_forhtm, 2008.
- (33) Ditter, K. C.; Crowe, E. H.; Mendez-Figueroa, H.; Wagner, S.; Gupta, M.; Chauhan, S. P.; Blackwell, S. C. Accuracy of Baseline Prevalence Estimates for Sample Size Calculations in Obstetrical Randomized Controlled Trials. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* **2022**, *226* (6), 855–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2022.01.032>.
- (34) Weaver, C. S.; Leonardi-Bee, J.; Bath-Hextall, F. J.; Bath, P. M. W. Sample Size Calculations in Acute Stroke Trials: A Systematic Review of Their Reporting, Characteristics, and Relationship With Outcome. *Stroke* **2004**, *35* (5), 1216–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.STR.0000125010.70652.93>.
- (35) Bamber, D.; Collins, H. E.; Powell, C.; Gonçalves, G. C.; Johnson, S.; Manktelow, B.; Ornelas, J. P.; Lopes, J. C.; Rocha, A.; Draper, E. S. Development of a Data Classification System for Preterm Birth Cohort Studies: The RECAP Preterm Project. *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* **2022**, *22* (1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01494-5>.
- (36) Powell, C.; Bamber, D.; Collins, H. E.; Draper, E. S.; Manktelow, B.; Kajante, E.; Cuttini, M.; Wolke, D.; Maier, R. F.; Zeitlin, J.; Johnson, S. Recommendations for Data Collection in Cohort Studies of Preterm Born Individuals – The RECAP Preterm Core Dataset. *Paediatr. Perinat. Epidemiol.* **2024**, *38* (7), 615–623. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppe.13096>.
- (37) Speich, B. Adequate Reporting of the Sample Size Calculation in Surgical Randomized Controlled Trials. *Surgery* **2020**, *167* (5), 812–814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surg.2019.10.011>.